

Rate of seed set appears to be the most stable yield component, followed by 1,000-grain weight, plant height, panicle

length, and harvest index (see table). The most unstable traits are grain yield/plant, total weight/plant, and panicle/plant.

Two or three seedlings/hill appears to yield best. ■

Effect of seedlings/hill on plant yield and yield components. Wuhan, China, 1989.

Seedlings/hill (no.)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/hill (no.)	Panicles/plant (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets/panicle (no.)		Seed-set rate (%)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield/hill (g)	Grain yield/plant (g)	Grain weight/hill (g)	Grain weight/plant (g)	Harvest index
					Fertile	Total							
1	79.0	5.0	5.0	18.0	74.6	83.4	89.4	24.3	9.2	9.2	15.6	15.6	0.5
2	82.2	5.6	2.8	18.7	72.7	81.3	89.4	24.4	9.9	5.0	15.6	7.8	0.5
3	81.8	7.4	2.5	17.4	74.1	82.2	90.1	23.5	12.9	4.3	21.8	7.3	0.5
4	80.4	9.0	2.3	17.0	61.5	69.9	88.0	23.7	13.0	3.2	23.4	5.8	0.4
5	84.4	10.4	2.1	17.3	58.0	66.0	87.8	23.5	14.1	2.8	26.2	5.2	0.4
Mean	81.6	7.5	2.9	17.7	68.2	76.6	89.0	23.9	11.8	4.9	20.5	8.4	0.5
CV (%)	2.5	30.4	40.1	3.7	11.5	10.5	1.1	1.8	18.2	51.6	23.2	50.1	5.5

Integrated pest management — diseases

Status of rice blast (BI) in eastern Uttar Pradesh, India

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Rice is primarily grown as a hot-wet season (1 Jun-30 Nov) crop in eastern UP. Before the introduction of TN1, IR8, Jaya, and other high-yielding varieties, BI affected extensive rainfed rice areas. With the introduction of modern varieties, the area under irrigation increased. Varietal resistance and less frequent moisture stress reduced early and severe BI attack. With the consequent reduction in inoculum load and discontinued use of susceptible varieties, the area affected by BI shrank considerably.

By mid-1970s, BI had been confined to the submountain regions of Gonda, Bahraich, Basti, and Gorakhpur districts, (the eastern tarai). There, nearness to inoculum from Nepal and much more frequent cultivation of susceptible traditional rainfed varieties made it possible for the disease to recur each year.

The disease starts at the seedling stage (May) and eventually covers leaves, sheaths, nodes, panicle stalk, panicle node, and panicle proper. In years with several drought stress periods of 10 d or more, rainfed rice becomes uneconomic to harvest.

Our surveys of farmers' fields and experimental plots 1977-89 indicate BI incidence in the eastern plains as well. Jarhan seedlings raised under rainfed conditions at Faizabad are infected by Jul and, in years with even short droughts, are defoliated by mid-August. Under irrigation, foliar BI pressure remains low even on varieties that are susceptible when grown under rainfed conditions.

Neck BI is common to all ecosystems, both in the tarai and in the eastern plains. With the introduction of neck BI-susceptible varieties, it has become a serious problem. BI is increasing in extent and intensity with the increase of the area under better fertility. ■

Distribution of bacterial blight (BB) in Nepal

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We surveyed 32 rice-growing districts in the Terai and important rice-growing districts in the hills to map the distribution of BB disease. Areas inspected were mostly along the national highways. Disease incidence was calculated on a 1-m² area at each site as number of infected leaves/hill × 100.

Table 1. Distribution of BB in Nepal, 1986-89.

District	Sites surveyed (no.)	Average field infection (%)
Jhapa	5	>50
Morang	4	>50
Sunsari	3	10-25
Dhankuta	2	10-25
Saptari	3	26-50
Dhanusa	7	10-25
Siraha	6	10-25
Mahotari	6	10-25
Sarlahi	5	26-50
Rautahat	2	10-25
Bara	13	>50
Parsa	15	>50
Chitwan	6	10-25
Nawalparasi	4	10-25
Rupandehi	7	26-50
Kapilvastu	4	10-25
Dang	8	26-50
Banke	5	10-25
Bardiya	6	10-25
Kailali	4	26-25
Kanchanpur	12	>50
Palpa	2	26-50
Syanja	3	10-25
Kaski	3	26-50
Tanahu	5	>50
Gorkha	1	<10
Kathmandu	5	>50
Bhaktapur	6	10-25
Lalitpur	4	10-25
Nuwakot	5	<10
Kabhre	4	10-25
Sindhuli	5	10-25
Total	170	

Terai districts Jhapa, Morang, Bara, Parsa, and Kanchanpur had the highest BB infection (Table 1). In the hills, Tanahu and Kathmandu districts had the highest.